

Multiple Zones in Paper Electro-Chromatography

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The occurrence of more than one spot when there would be one only in the chromatogram has led to a detailed study of the problem. Keller and Giddings¹ have made a critical study of the views prevalent on the topic, from which it becomes clear that the problem is more complex than it appears. A number of possibilities are there to give rise to multiple spots in the chromatogram. Amongst these are (i) chemical reaction between the developing agent and the solute; (ii) impurities in the solution itself; (iii) discontinuities in the immobile and mobile phases; (iv) overloading of the initial zone; (v) the heterogeneity of the paper and (vi) formation of charged species and complexes. The last one which is of more important consideration than the others in the case of electro-migration of inorganic ions on paper, may be very complicated indeed. Keller and Giddings (*loc. cit.*) have attempted to find out on the basis of theoretical consideration alone the number and nature of spots that will be obtained when a single substance is electrochromatographed.

In electro-chromatography as has been done in the present study chemical reaction is likely to take place between the products of the electrolysis and the migrating solute. The kinetics of this reaction may under suitable conditions lead to multiplicity of zones. Without any direct proof of the nature of the products of electrolysis, which might react with the solute, considerable speculation is possible. An explanation of the multiple spots and the nature of the probable chemical species has been offered in the examples cited below.

(a) Zinc nitrate solution in decinormal potassium nitrate or 0.2N potassium nitrate, when electrochromatographed using the common technique² (inverted V typed Durrum's Set), shows two zones after 10 hours' run and developed with dithiazone. One of these is the principal zone due to Zn^{2+} ions, which moves towards the cathode, and the other is faint one moving towards the anode and may be due to ZnO_2^{-2} ions. The latter is likely to result from the reaction between Zn^{2+} and OH^- ions.

(b) H_2PtCl_6 in 0.1N hydrochloric acid or 0.05N hydrochloric acid shows similarly two bands³ after 10 hours' run and development with $SnCl_2$ which may be respectively due to $(PtCl_5, H_2O)^-$ or $(PtCl_5, OH)^{-2}$ and $PtCl_6^{-2}$. In presence of glycerol used with the carrier electrolyte only one species is observed. Since glycerol is likely to prevent hydration the first species observed in absence of glycerol is possibly due to the hydrated $(PtCl_5, H_2O)^-$ and not $(PtCl_5OH)^{-2}$.

(c) Bismuth nitrate shows after 5 hours' run in 0.1N potassium iodide three distinct zones. That due to Bi^{3+} moves towards the cathode and is precipitated as a dark brown zone, is caused by BiI_3 . The second one forms the orange coloured zone of BiOI formed from BiO^+ ion which is perhaps the species formed during the course of the reaction. A yellow coloured anionic complex moves towards the anode and constitutes the third spot obtained in the electro-chromatogram of $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ in KI. Individual cases may be interpreted in this way; it is to be understood that more than one kind of speculation may "explain things" but only direct proofs can decide interpretations.

In order to observe the effect of protecting the migrating ion from the products of electrolysis, the platinum electrodes and the electrode vessels are separated by means of agar-KNO₃ salt bridges, from the carrier electrolyte vessels into which the ends of the paper strip dip (Fig. 1) and the already mentioned three experiments are carried out.

Fig 1

(d) The migration of zinc ions in decinormal potassium nitrate under this condition shows only one zone instead of two after 10 hours' run and this zone as Zn^{2+} ions moves towards the cathode and the feeble zone due to probably ZnO_2^{-2} ions moving towards the anode disappears due to protection of Zn^{2+} ions from chemical reaction with the OH^- ions (one of the products of electrolysis).

(e) Again H_2PtCl_6 in 0.1N HCl or 0.05N HCl shows similarly only one band after 10 hrs' run due to movement of PtCl_6^{-2} ions and the other band does not form at all probably for the same reason.

(f) Bi^{3+} ions, however, in 0.1N KI show after 5 hrs' run two zones instead of three, of which one zone is due to cationic movement of Bi, Bi^{3+} as simple cation and subsequent precipitation as dark brown zone as BiI_3 and the second zone is due to anionic movement and the yellow colour of the zone is due to formation of BiI_4^- complex. The disappearance of the third zone is due to the fact that the migrant is protected from coming into reaction with the products of electrolysis.

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